

Optical investigation of pure and potassium bromide (KBr) doped PVDF/PEO electrolyte thin films.

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Abstract

Solution casting was used to create solid polymer electrolyte films based on polymer blends of polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and polyethylene oxide (PEO), with varying percentages of KBr. Ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy was used for optical research. By altering the KBr concentrations, these films' optical characteristics were changed. According to the data, increasing the quantity of salt causes the absorption edge of electrolyte samples to shift towards a lower energy area, resulting in a reduction of the band gap. According to the band gap energy data, adding KBr to the polymeric system results in charge transfer complexes in the blend polymer. These complexes raise the electrical conductivity of the system by adding extra charges to the lattice. Key words: PVDF and PEO based polymer electrolyte films, Ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy, and optical absorption.

1. Introduction

The primary issues facing society are the generation, delivery, and storage of energy. Ion-conducting solid polymer electrolytes are key components of many electrochemical devices, including sensors, solar cells, supercapacitors, and rechargeable batteries, because of this [1-6]. Salt can complexate with a variety of polymer hosts, including PEO, PEG, PPO, PVP, PMMA, and PVA, to generate ion-conducting polymer electrolytes.

Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) is one of these polymers that merits special consideration due to its charge transfer mechanism, good electrical characteristics, and ease of processing [7]. The stiff pyrrolidone group, which is present in PVDF, an amorphous polymer, gives it a high T_g and is known to form a variety of complexes with numerous inorganic salts [8]. The optical qualities, surface resistance, non-tracking features, high resistance, and good compatibility with other polymers are all possessed by polyethylene oxide (PEO). The significant effects of PEO on the electrode-electrolyte interface stabilization were explained by Appetecchi et al. [9]. Iijima et al.'s initial research on the plasticized polymer electrolytes used PEO as a host [10]. Furthermore, Bohnke [11] investigated the stability and kinetics of lithium electrodes in gel electrolytes based on PEO. Taking the aforementioned into consideration, the current work attempts to carry out optical investigations of polymer blend electrolyte systems based on polyethylene oxide (PEO) and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) complexed with potassium bromide (KBr).

2. Experimental

Preparation of film (120 μ m) of pure PVDF /PEO mixture and various composition of complexed film (PVDF / PEO) containing KBr salt Preparation of films in weight percent ratio (47,5:47,5:05) (45,45:10) and (42,5:42,15) Solution casting technique (using double distilled water) PVDF /PEO + KBr salt dissolved in double distilled water

and mixed at room temperature (10–12 hours) to obtain homogeneous mixture Procedure of casting the solution on polypropylene dish Evaporation of the solvent at room temperature Dried composite polymer films peeled off from polypropylene dish and stored in dry vacuum box.

The UV-Vis assimilation spectra of arranged tests were recorded within the extend 200–900 nm at room temperature employing a JASCO UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer (demonstrate V.700). From these information, optical constants such as band edges and optical band holes, both coordinate and circuitous, were decided.

3. Result & Discussions

The electron transition from the top of the valence band to the bottom of the conduction band is primarily responsible for the UV absorption. As illustrated in Fig.1, the room temperature UV-vis absorption spectra of the blend PVDF/PEO and PVDF/PEO/KBr solid polymer electrolyte films are obtained in the wavelength range of 200-900 nm. The carbonyl group of the pure polymer blend is responsible for the shoulder-like peak that can be seen in the spectrum of the pure PVDF/PEO polymer blend film at about 238 nm, as shown in Figure. In doped film, the absorption coefficient rises with increasing doping level and the shoulder shifts towards higher wavelengths. The strong interaction between PVDF/PEO and KBr salt, as well as the increase in carbonyl groups, could be the cause of this [12].

Fig. 1. UV-Vis absorption spectra of (a) pure PVDF+PEO (b) (PVDF+PEO+KBr) (50:45:5) ;(c) (PVDF+PEO+KBr) (50:40:10); (d) (PVDF+PEO+KBr) (50:35:15) films.

Optical constants like the optical band gap (E_g) and the location of the fundamental band edge are found through optical absorption studies of the films. The absorption edge's primary characteristic is the absorption coefficient's (α) exponential rise with photon energy ($h\nu$). The formula can be used to determine the absorption coefficient α from the spectra [Fig. 2].

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{A}{d}\right) * 2.303 \quad (1)$$

where d is the sample's thickness and A is the absorbance. The absorption edge is located at 3.87 eV for pure PVDF/PEO films and decreases 3.70 to 3.44 eV for doped films.

Fig. 2. : α vs. $h\nu$ plots of (a) pure PVDF+PEO (b) (PVDF+PEO +KBr)(50:45:5) (c) (PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50:40:10); (d) (PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50:35:15) films.

The absorption coefficient depends on the incident photon's energy in the following ways when a direct band gap is present [13, 14, 15].

$$\alpha h\nu = c(h\nu - E_g)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (2)$$

Where h is the Planck's constant, ν is the light frequency, c is a constant, and E_g is the band gap. A linear relationship is observed between $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ and $h\nu$ (photon energy), as illustrated in Figure 3. The band gap can be calculated by extrapolating the linear portion of the curve to zero absorption value and finding the intercept on the

energy axis. The direct band gap for pure PVDF/PEO film is 3.99 eV, and the values for doped films range from 3.95 to 3.78 eV (see table 1.1).

Fig. 3. : $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ plots of (a) pure PVDF+PEO (b) (PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50:45:5) (c) (PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50:40:10); (d) (PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50:35:15) films.

The absorption coefficient's dependence on photon energy is as follows for indirect transitions that need phonon assistance [13, 14, 15,].

$$\alpha h\nu = A(h\nu - E_g + E_p)^2 + B(h\nu - E_g - E_p)^2 \quad (3)$$

where A and B are constants that depend on the band structure, and E_p is the phonon energy connected to the transition. As illustrated in Fig. 4, the plots of $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$ yielded the indirect band gaps. The indirect band gap for pure PVDF/PEO film is 3.89 eV, whereas the values for doped films range from 3.81 to 3.59 eV.

Fig. 4. : $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$ plots of (a) pure PVDF+PEO (b) (PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50:45:5) (c) (PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50:40:10); (d) (PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50:35:15) films.

The table displays the absorption edge and direct and indirect band gap energies of the pure and NaBr-doped PVDF/PEO polymer films that were obtained in this work.1.

Table.1: Absorption edge optical band gap values of pure and Na doped PVA/PEG films.

Concentration (Weight %)	Absorption edge (eV)	Optical band gap energy(eV)	
		Direct	Indirect
PVDF+PEO	3.87	3.99	3.89
(PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50+45+5)	3.70	3.95	3.81
(PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50+40+10)	3.61	3.89	3.69
(PVDF+PEO + KBr) (50+35+15)	3.44	3.78	3.59

Table 1 shows that as the doping level increases, the values of the direct and indirect band gaps decrease. The development of defects in the polymeric matrix could be the cause of this decline. The decrease in band gap energy is caused by these defects, which result in localized states in the optical band gap that overlap with the band system. This suggests that PVDF/PEO films become more semiconducting in nature as the concentration of KBr as a dopant increases [16, 17].

Conclusions

A casting strategy was used to arrange the strong polymer electrolyte movies PVDF/PEO/KBr, which are then characterized using UV-Vis spectroscopy. A diminishing drift with expanded KBr salt substance was observed in the optical retention edge and optical band crevice (coordinate and roundabout), which was attributed to the charge exchange arrangement.

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